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10th December 1972

Dear Mr. Williamson,

Miss de Cardi has told me that you have received some Palaeolithic material during a survey of the Iranian littoral and I should greatly appreciate some further details. In 1970 I was the archaeological member of a party which made a search in N.W. Iran, mainly Azerbaijan, for Lower Palaeolithic material. We found one rolled, surface hand-axe! Since then I have been following up any reports I hear of Lower Palaeolithic material anywhere in Iran. There is a little from Baluchistan and I suspect that any route between Africa and India was along the southern littoral, so I am most interested to learn what you found.

Yours sincerely,

J.J. Wymer

Mr. Andrew Williamson, M.A.,
West End,
Wootton,
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